

depending upon the amount incorporated in the soil. We studied N release from sesbania green manure and its effect on timing fertilizer N application.

Soil of the experiment was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with 5 mm percolation/h. It had pH 8.4, EC 0.15 mmho/cm, 0.34% organic carbon, 0.06% N, and 8 $\mu\text{g/g}$ KCl-extractable $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$. Finely chopped 2-mo-old fresh sesbania was mixed 20% by volume with soil with and without fertilizer N. The soil samples were submerged and incubated at $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Three samples from each treatment were taken at 4, 7, 14, 28, 42, and 56 d of incubation and extracted with 2 N KCl to determine $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content (Fig. 1).

In a field experiment, 2-mo-old sesbania, equivalent to 22 t green matter/ha and 120 kg N/ha, was incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice on 10 Jul 1984. All but the no-green-manure plots received the same amount of sesbania. At last puddling, 26-30 kg PK/ha was applied

to all plots. Urea N at 40-120 kg/ha was applied in different combinations at transplanting or 21 or 42 d after transplanting (DT). The crop was harvested at maturity and grain yield was determined at 14% moisture content.

The kinetics of KCl-extractable $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ indicated that sesbania began releasing N soon after incorporation. At 4 d of incubation, 44 and 23 mg $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N/kg}$ was received in soil with sesbania, with and without applied N. Peak $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ was within 7 to 14 d of sesbania incor-

poration and release remained steady through 56 d.

Data indicated that incorporating sesbania alone gave yield as high as applying 120 kg N/ha as urea (Fig. 2). Furthermore, with sesbania, applying 40-60 kg fertilizer N/ha at 42 DT gave yields at par with treatments where N was applied at transplanting or 21 DT. Sesbania-N was sufficient for rice at early growth stages. Topdressing 40 kg N/ha at 42 DT was necessary in lowland rice with incorporated sesbania. □

Effect of seeding rate and N levels on yield of direct-seeded rice

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We evaluated IR21717-42-1 performance at different seeding rates and N levels on a Ustifluent soil with pH 5.7 at Chau Thanh District, An Giang Province. N was applied at 40, 70, 100, or 130 kg/ha in

main plots and seeding rates were 200, 250, 300, 350, or 400 kg seed/ha in subplots. The experiment was in three replications. After land preparation, excess water was drained away and 13 kg P/ha as superphosphate was broadcast. Pregerminated seed was broadcast on uniformly puddled soil on 15 May 1983. N was applied, one-half at 20 d after sowing (DS) and in equal splits at 30 and 45 DS. Rice was harvested 18 Aug and yield was estimated from an 18-m² area.

Interaction between seeding rate and N level was significant. It was not possible to increase yield by increasing seeding rate beyond 200 kg/ha (see table). Data indicate that seeding rate might be reduced below 200 kg/ha without affecting yield. □

Grain yield as influenced by seed rate and N level, An Giang Province, Vietnam.

Seeding rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean
	40 kg N/ha	70 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	130 kg N/ha	
200	3.9	4.7	4.8	5.0	4.6
250	3.9	4.7	4.7	5.0	4.6
300	4.0	4.4	4.8	4.7	4.5
350	4.0	4.3	4.5	4.2	4.4
400	3.8	4.3	4.3	4.1	4.1
Mean	3.9	4.5	4.6	4.6	
<i>Main effects</i>		CD at 5%		CV (%)	
Seed rate (S)		0.2		6.7	
N level (N)		0.4		10.0	
<i>Interaction effects</i>					
Seed rate at a constant N level		0.3			
N at a constant S level		0.5			

Comparison of chemical indices for available K for rice in alluvial soils of Punjab

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We compared different soil tests for available K in 20 soils and their relationship to rice yield and K uptake in the greenhouse. Soils had pH 8.7 ± 0.4 , electrical conductivity 0.52 ± 0.26 mmho/cm, $0.44 \pm 0.18\%$ organic C, 57.4 ± 17.6 ppm $\text{KMnO}_4\text{-N}$, and 2.2 ± 1.1 ppm Olsen-P. Five 20-d-old PR106 seedlings grown in a K deficient solution were transplanted into pots each with 4.5 kg soil.

Treatments were 0 and 21 ppm K as KCl. A basal dose of 50 ppm N and 11 ppm P was applied to all pots and 50 ppm

N was added 3 wk after transplanting. The crop was harvested at maturity and grain and straw yields recorded. The grain and straw samples were digested in a diacid (HNO₃ + HClO₄ in 4:1 ratio) mixture and analyzed for K. Percent yield or K uptake was calculated:

$$\text{Percent yield or K uptake} = \frac{\text{yield or K uptake without K treatment}}{\text{yield or K uptake with applied K}} \times 100$$

Available K in soil was extracted using IN neutral ammonium acetate (1:5 soil: solution, 5 min shaking); 0.5 M sodium bicarbonate of pH 8.5 (1:20 soil: solution, 30 min shaking); Morgan's reagent 3% acetic acid + 10% sodium acetate of pH 4.8 (1:5 soil:solution, 5 min shaking); 1% citric acid (1: 10 soil:solution, 4 h shaking); Troug's reagent 0.002 N H₂SO₄ + 0.3% (NH₄)₂SO₄ with pH 3.0 (1:200 soil:solution, 30 min shaking); and boiling nitric acid (boiling 2.5 g soil in 25 ml IN HNO₃ for 10 min and 4 washings, each with 15 ml of 0.1N cold HNO₃ to make volume to 100 ml). Simple correlation coefficients were calculated for yield and K-uptake parameters with K indices (see table).

Grain yield varied from 8.5 to 44.5 g/pot in the control and 14.4 to 57.4 g/pot in treated pots. Total dry matter (grain + straw) yield varied from 25.4 to 102.1 g/pot and 38.8 to 107.5 g/pot in control and K-treated pots. Total K uptake by grain and straw ranged from 150 to 1,182 mg/pot in control and 280 to 1,373 mg/

Determining available K by different indices and their relation to rice plant parameters, Ludhiana, India.^a

	NH ₄ OAC	NaHCO ₃	Morgan	Citric acid	Troug	Nitric acid
	<i>Available K (ppm)</i>					
Range	26.3-179.9	50.0-270.1	62.5-325.0	29.9-195.1	9.8-220.1	533.0-2397.8
Mean	83.0 (±43.8)	127.7 (±64.5)	170.0 (±88.2)	101.0 (±53.0)	101.0 (±73.6)	1485.0 (±498.0)
	<i>Correlation coefficient (r-value)</i>					
Control grain yield	0.300	0.580**	0.438	0.398	0.335	0.340
Control dry matter yield	0.168	0.461*	0.300	0.263	0.163	0.198
Control grain K uptake	0.292	0.525*	0.437	0.374	0.345	0.331
Control dry matter K uptake	0.305	0.572**	0.444*	0.405	0.315	0.345
Percent grain yield	-0.234	0.085	0.044	-0.126	-0.205	0.080
Percent dry matter yield	-0.397	0.055	-0.100	-0.282	-0.330	0.092
Percent grain K uptake	-0.208	-0.032	-0.028	-0.156	-0.111	-0.023
Percent dry matter K uptake	-0.254	0.07	-0.605	-0.208	-0.235	0.150

^aSignificant at 5% (*) or 1% (**) levels; dry matter = grain + straw.

pot in K-treated pots. Grain yield varied from 59 to 98% and K uptake from 47 to 96%. Only in 6 soils was the response in yield or K uptake due to applied K above 20%. Results indicate that 2 to 41% of the yield obtained and 4 to 53% of K uptake could be attributed to applied K.

The correlation between control grain yield and control K uptake with K extracted by 0.5 M NaHCO₃ was highly significant ($r = 0.580^{**}$ and 0.572^{**}). Other methods related poorly with plant parameters. The prediction value (r^2) for the highest correlation of $r = 0.580$ was 33.6%. Probably the low response to

applied K in these soils resulted in low predictability for the indices. When different indices of K availability were related, we found that K extracted by 0.5 M NaHCO₃ was highly and significantly correlated with NH₄OAC extractable K ($r = 0.788^{**}$), suggesting that the former extractant can be satisfactorily used to estimate available K in the soils while also determining available P (0.5 M NaHCO₃ is an accepted method for estimating available P in these soils) in a single extraction. Soils with less than 72 ppm NaHCO₃-K are low in available K. □

Effect of N level on aged rice seedlings

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We studied tillering capacity, grain yield, and duration of IR20 at two seedling ages and different N levels in a randomized block design at TNRRI in 1983-84 winter.

Single 40- or 60-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 0 N, 100 kg N (50+25+25), 150 kg N (100+25+25), or 200 kg N (150+25+25)/ha as basal plus 2 top-dressings. Plots received 50 kg P and potash/ha basally.

Effect of seedling age and N level on IR20 duration, yield characters, and grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment N/ha)	Field duration (d)	Tillers/hill	Productive tillers/hill	Dry matter (t/ha)	Grain yield	
					kg/ha daily	t/ha
<i>40-d seedlings</i>						
0 N	103	5.8	5.3	7	26	2.7
50+25+25	110	8.5	8.1	16	37	4.1
100+25+25	111	9.4	8.9	17	39	4.4
150+25+25	111	9.8	8.1	19	41	4.5
<i>60-d seedlings</i>						
0 N	99	6.3	5.9	6	21	2.0
50+25+25	107	8.8	7.6	13	32	3.4
100+25+25	111	9.5	8.4	14	35	3.9
150+25+25	114	9.2	8.2	15	36	4.2
LSD (0.05)						
Treatments	1.5	1.2	1.2	2	3	0.3
Seedling age	ns	ns	ns	1	1	0.2
N	1.0	0.9	0.8	1	2	0.2